

The Turkish quarters are the highly segregated areas.

The Jewish neighbourhoods perform two major clusters; parts of them are identical to the Jewish slums that the 1890 fire destroyed. These highly segregated areas are closest to the city's integrating core.

The most segregated lines in the Greek neighbourhoods pass by their socio-cultural centres.

The market area is also segregated from the outside world. It is linked to the harbour and guilds centre (Venizelou St.).

The integration core in 1891 plan remains largely stable.

"Ano-Polis" and the lower Turkish quarters remain deep and poorly integrated (map 3). The same applies to the wholesale market area as well as the Greek and Jewish quarters. Areas where there is a slight or major shift from the previous plan are:

i) the Jewish and Greek quarters redesigned after the 1890 fire; despite of the alteration of their spatial morphology, they remain poorly integrated to the city's global structure; nevertheless, some of the rebuilt synagogues or the old Greek churches become close to these integrating lines. The old Jewish centre - Ravinias Sq.- remains segregated.

ii) the core is strengthened by a set of lines running parallel to Egnatia St. and southwards of it.

iii) there are less links from the core to the Turkish quarters and this indicates that the Turks had been highly isolated in the last years before 1891.

It is of some importance to investigate the four major subsystems, that is the three residential areas occupied by the three distinct ethnicities and market areas (maps 4,5,6).

i) There is an overlap between the city's major core and the Turkish

one. The latter penetrates more deeply the upper quarters, but nevertheless, it leaves most of this area almost purely segregated. St. Demetrious, old Aristotelous and Kassandros Sts. as well as a number of short perpendicular lines form a gridiron core coinciding with the administration area of the whole city.

ii) The double focused core of the market area is formed by Venizelou St. and both sides of Salaminos St. that link market with the harbour area. Venizelou St. is the link between Turkish and market areas as well as Egnatia St. The core also links the major streets of Jewish quarters eastward with the Turkish market westwards and integrates land uses such as Besesteni (commercial centre), retail shops and workshops, public baths, the wholesale market ("Istira"), Turkish mosques, banks and financial institutions.

iii) the Jewish and Greek quarters have their own cores fragmented in some lines almost in their heart and some others in the periphery, hardly overlapping the major core. The streets opened in 1891 are within the local cores.

In the Jewish quarters the cultural centre remains out of their own core. The latter integrates some of the schools, public baths, as well as new social centres.

The core in the Greek quarters does not integrate their social centres. The Greek churches transformed to mosques become integrated to the major core.

iv) In market areas the most segregated lines are one step away from the integrating core.

v) The Jewish segregated areas include most of their cultural centres.

vi) In Greek quarters the most segregated lines are found close to their socio-cultural centres such as churches and schools.

The integration attributes of "ethno-quarters" are presented in maps 5,5.a. There it has been revealed that

i) the links between neighbourhoods of different ethnicities are minimal, especially between the Turkish and Greek ones.

ii) the public thoroughfares are highly accessible in the Turkish quarters, rather directly accessible in the Jewish ones and almost unaccessible in the Greek ones (in the last open public spaces are absent).

iii) the mix of uses is reduced from the Turkish, the Jewish to the Greek quarters.

"Ano-Polis" considered as a unique subsystem,

i) none of its integrating lines traverse its borders (highly isolated area).

ii) the integration core is split into five sub-units integrating either major squares or major routes leading to the frontiers, local streets with commercial activities or/and some public buildings. Furthermore, most of the muslim educational buildings and monasteries remain isolated in its most segregated clusters (map 5.1).

Concluding, the city is a self-contained spatial system with limited links with the carrier.

The core facilitates the direct accessibility of the visitors to the city's heart (market areas); it is further strengthened by streets internal to the initial system linking between each other the various "ethnoquarters" and market areas; thus, it seems to integrate the parts of the city to a central structure providing a domain where people are aware of each other's presence and interact, while it leaves to the most segregated clusters the main residential areas. It also integrates the major Turkish public buildings and open spaces and leaves out the Jewish and Greek ones. The

redesign of some Jewish and Greek quarters in 1891 does not integrate better their socio-cultural centres, but some new commercial streets. Besides, it is identical to the core of the original hellenistic and roman major grid. The ancient "Agora" or roman "Forum" remains highly segregated.

The overlap with the market's double core makes the links with the harbour and the rest of the city and integrates the most important commercial uses and the hybrid tertiary sector. The most segregated lines include some of the city's main markets.

The overlap between the city's core and the Turkish one integrates the major administrative and cultural centre of the city and the major public buildings and open spaces of the community.

"Ano-Polis", a highly isolated area, integrates the main public buildings and open spaces of the Turks.

The Jewish and Greek cores do not overlap the major one; they do not integrate their socio-cultural centres either. The Greek churches transformed to mosques became integrated to the major core.

The most segregated parts of the overall urban system include mainly purely residential areas with an almost absolutely defined ethnical identity or/and public buildings serving corresponding socio-cultural purposes (i.e. intimacy).

In Greek quarters the core does not integrate the ethnicity's social centres that are in the heart of the most segregated clusters or, even more, the heart of the building blocks where the entrance belongs to -and is controlled by- the landowners of the nearby lots. The social centres are up to nine steps away from the ethnicity's core. Furthermore, most of the highly accessible lines cluster along the borders of the quarters forming a barrier to the neighbouring Turkish areas and discouraging oppressors to

enter.

In the scale of the neighbourhood, accessibility to public buildings and open spaces is highest in the Turkish and lowest in the Greek quarters. The interlinks between neighbourhoods of different ethnicities are also minimum, especially between the Greeks and the Turks.

6.1.2. Control values (CV) -Intelligibility (I)

(maps 7,8,9,9.a, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15)

Map 7 shows the 103 lines responsible for the 10% higher control values of the spatial system.

The control core

a) makes full use of the city's entrances and the links with the carrier.

b) links directly the market and harbour areas and loosely the three distinct communities,

c) most of the high control lines in the gravity centre of the city belong to the city's integration core (lines 1,2,3,7,10,13,14,15,16,18,22,37,38,41,44,60,63,67,84,98,101).

The control core is more spread than the integration one: high global intelligibility is distributed at a broader area than the most accessible parts; hence, there is a smooth reduction of high control values and intelligibility from the city's core to its parts (map 8). Furthermore, since all lines helping access from the outside are of high control and integration values, a lot of spatial control and intelligibility is invested on the in and out flow of visitors. Besides, a certain proportion of the highest control values has been invested in the market and harbour areas.

Areas of high control and low integration values are

- a) clusters in the wholesale and retail markets
- b) the Jewish quarters
- c) the Greek "
- d) the Turkish " (maps 9,10).

When considered as self-contained units,

i) the wholesale and retail markets have their highest control- values lines overlapping their integration core (high intelligibility, map 9.a).

High control values form a TT-shape link with Egnatia St., safeguarding a continual flow of people along this route or distributing them to the harbour area and retail market eastward Venizelou St. There are also some other lines of strong control and integration values in Tophane and retail market in Jewish quarters as well as the lower streets parallel to the coast. Therefore, high intelligibility is continual in the whole market area (map 9.3). Some highly segregated lines afford strong control values: "Ladadika", "Tophane" and the rest of the market areas, although not very easily accessible from the city's core, are locally highly constituted.

The high integration and low control values at the harbour seem to encourage more strangers than inhabitants to move around it.

ii) In Jewish area most of the integrating lines maintaining direct links with the neighbouring areas become lines of strong control as well. This does not happen in the heart of the area: high intelligibility has been kept at the shallowest parts of the "ethno-quarters" and strangers are not permitted to penetrate its heart.

Lines with high control and low integration values form a continual network: the areas are highly intelligible only for their own inhabitants; furthermore, a certain number of the Jewish socio-religious centres are on

lines of strong control and integration values and only a few of them are on low-values lines.

iii) Along the periphery of the Greek area five out of the eleven most integrated lines are lines of strong control (lines 2,3,4,9,10): the area as a whole had been highly intelligible along its borders and discouraged strangers to penetrate it. Lines of high control value appear to pass close to the socio-ethnic and educational centres of the community, but they hardly control them: the community centres are of low intelligibility. In "Ano-Polis" they are of even lower control values.

When old Greek centres are converted to Islamic ones their surrounding area has usually low control values.

iv) In the Turkish area the longest lines at its lower part are of high control and integration values: the administration and other public buildings allocated here (lines 1,2,3,5,6,7,10,13,15,27,54) are of high intelligibility.

Again, the links with "Ano-Polis" are very weak: even the city's inhabitants were discouraged to visit it (map 11). There is also a major discontinuity with Lower City high control-value lines (map 12); low values are also found along the frontiers. In the area itself the Turkish public buildings and open public spaces are highly intelligible.

The area north-westwards Egnatia St. has some lines with strong control and integration values (lines 2,13,27,39); this is the highly intelligible Turkish area. Lines of high control values accompanied by high or low integration values carry major public buildings or/and open public spaces (highly intelligible).

Summarising the findings in "ethnoquarters" (map 13), highly intelligible are:

a) in Turkish quarters the public buildings, open public spaces and central-area-functions.

b) in Jewish quarters the links with the Turkish neighbourhoods and market areas, some of their socio-cultural centres and the Turkish major public buildings,

c) in Greek quarters only the superimposed Turkish public buildings and some of the commercial activities; their socio-cultural centres, as well as the links with other ethno-quarters are poorly intelligible.

d) market areas are characterised by high control and intelligibility values along their borders and major commercial streets.

Concluding, the city's control core overlaps and is more expanded than the integration one. The intelligibility of space is achieved at its major "supergrid" linking directly the city's entrances with the main commercial streets and market areas. Some special markets are highly locally constituted and intelligible. The harbour area is highly intelligible as well.

In Jewish areas high control and intelligibility values are fragmented along the borders with the market areas. There are no links with the Greek quarters. Highly locally constituted and intelligible are the commercial streets, most of the Turkish public buildings and some of their old synagogues. The movement of inhabitants in their own area is encouraged through a continual network of highly locally constituted places not easily accessible by strangers.

In "Malta" area lines of high control values carry the city's tertiary sector and other central-area functions.

In Greek areas the high control values and intelligibility are mainly fragmented at their periphery. Almost all their socio-cultural centres are

steps away from the highly locally constituted spaces (low intelligibility). The christian churches converted to mosques remain locally constituted (low intelligibility); in "Ano-Polis" the churches are in the heart of the building blocks (no intelligibility). In contrast, the superimposed Turkish public buildings are highly intelligible.

In Turkish quarters high control values and intelligibility are achieved at the administration centre, their public buildings and open spaces; the high constitution of their residential areas is disrupted only in "Ano-Polis". Even there, highly constituted lines carry almost all the major public buildings and open spaces. The area discourages -apart from strangers- the city's inhabitants themselves to visit it.

The lower class Turkish area north-westwards Egnatia St. is of high intelligibility.

The 1891 plan has not increased the global intelligibility since strong control lines are not integrating lines as well. It mainly improved the local constitution of space.

The overall structure of intelligibility cores in 1890 and 1891 plans reveals an intelligible network of streets immediately accessible to the entering strangers from which they could "read" a certain part of the overall spatial structure and orient themselves mainly in the city's market areas, while inhabitants were provided with poor internal intelligibility networks linked weakly with the major "supergrid" or disrupted from it altogether.

The 1891 plan increased the local intelligibility linking between themselves different ethnicities and favouring the function of market areas.

Considered in their own merits, the Turkish neighbourhoods provided

with high constitution and intelligibility their public buildings, public open spaces and central-area functions; the Jewish ones provided with the above high values their links with the market and Turkish neighbourhoods, some of their socio-cultural centres, less their public spaces and the Turkish public buildings; the Greek quarters provided with high values only the superimposed Turkish public buildings and some commercial activities while their socio-cultural centres and the links with the other "ethno-quarters" were provided even with negative values.

6.1.3. Choice values - Movement interface

(maps 16,17,18,18.a,19,20,21,22,23,24,25)

Map 16 shows the 101 lines of highest choice values (10% of the total choice value of the system).

The choice core is much more dispersed than the integration one forming major continuities in market, Jewish and Turkish areas while disrupted in Greek quarters and "Ano-Polis.

a) The choice core extends up to the six main entrances of the city. Lines starting from these entrances traverse the whole city's length (lines 15, 79,41,2,8 25,62,23,81,3).

b) The highest global-choice values belong to the vertical lines: most of the choice value had been invested on the internal movement of inhabitants linking the residential with market areas.

c) There is a striking overlap between the choice and integration cores (lines 8,2,41,12,13,11,47,24,67,49,3,81,83,23,62,1,68,20,27,6,40,72,5,7,14,9,78,58): in the formatted "supergrid" there has been achieved a movement

interface between the strangers and inhabitants (map 17).

d) The highest choice values are invested in market, Turkish and Jewish quarters and the least ones in the Greek quarters. Besides, in Turkish and market areas lines of the highest inhabitant-movement values are extensions of the major choice core.

e) Maps 18 and 18.a show the choice cores of all four subsystems. The "supergrid" is maintained with respect to the major lines of the overall integration and choice cores: the three ethnicities interact with strangers and among themselves along these streets that carry mainly the commercial and administration activities.

f) When maps 16 and 18 superimposed, it is revealed that while the city's choice core involves all three ethnicities to the continual distribution of movement of inhabitants and their interface with strangers, there emerge major disruptions of routes with high movement distribution in all the processed residential subsystems: the movement interface is encouraged at the peripheries of the subsystems and market areas and discouraged in their hearts (map 19).

g) In market areas the movement of inhabitants is continual and linked with the major core: They are best linked with the city's overall structure. Besides, most of their high choice-value lines belong in the city's choice core, too: it is in market areas that the highest movement interface takes place.

h) In Jewish areas the high choice value lines are unconnected and dispersed, in the oldest part hardly penetrating its heart. There are no major links with the Greek and Turkish quarters, but significant continuities with the market area.

Only a few of the latest synagogues are on high inhabitant-movement streets. In contrast, major Turkish public buildings are found along such

streets. In "Malta"area, the tertiary sector is rather of low IM and MI.

i) In Turkish areas the overlap between the ethnicity's and city's choice cores is in the administration centre. Some of the high-value lines pass by the old Greek churches converted to mosques or the community's religious centres and public open spaces. Major religious centres remain out of the major inhabitant-movement routes. In "Ano-Polis" the high choice-value lines form short, isolated clusters. If considered separately, the high-value lines link it weakly with Lower City and include major open spaces and most of the Turkish socio-cultural centres (maps 20,21).

j) In Greek area the movement of inhabitants is encouraged to flow at its periphery (map 18.a). Most of the penetrating high-value lines carry major Turkish public buildings. Again, the Greek social centres are two to five steps away from the high inhabitant-movement streets.

k) In most of the market, Turkish and to a less extent Jewish quarters, high-value lines are identical to parts of the major core or extend it up to their heart (map 22). This does not happen in Greek areas, where most of the high-value lines are disrupted far from the CH core.

The 1891 plan enhances the major pre-existing choice core at the city's borders: the "supergrid" is enhanced and broadened (lines 9,30,43,41,27). This applies even to the Greek quarters. In the Jewish area, the newly-traced streets favour the movement toward and from market areas, becoming thus, an area of "through movement" for the eastern Greek quarters (maps 23,24,25).

Concluding, the choice core overlaps and is more dispersed than the integration core. Highest movement interface is achieved in market areas. The vertical lines are more condensed than the horizontal ones favouring

more the internal movement of inhabitants toward market areas than the movement of visitors.

From all quarters, the Greek ones have the least and lowest density of movement interface isolated from the major core, while in almost all other areas, movement interface is an extension of the one in the major "supergrid".

In areas carrying commercial and administration activities, all three ethnicities interact between themselves and with strangers. In contrast, strangers are discouraged to enter purely residential areas: "through movement" is not favoured.

In market area there is a high movement interface at its periphery and its heart.

In Jewish area movement interface is discouraged at its heart: there are no links with the Greek and Turkish quarters, but significant continuities with the market area. In high movement interface streets there are more Turkish public buildings than synagogues and open public spaces of the community. In "Malta" area the tertiary sector is of low movement interface.

In Turkish areas the administration centre seems to be the most popular place for both strangers and inhabitants. All high movement interface streets carry the ethnicity's major public buildings or Greek churches converted to mosques as well as open public spaces. Some religious buildings are on low movement interface lines and this is closely related to their special use.

"Ano-Polis" is scarcely visited by the city's inhabitants and visitors; in its heart the high-value lines form short, isolated clusters involving the community's major public buildings and open spaces.

In Greek areas the high movement interface is maintained at the

periphery and the internal high-value routes carry mainly major Turkish public buildings, while the Greek ones are away even from the inhabitant movement routes. The flow of the Greeks in the market areas gains all the more major significance.

The 1891 plan enhances the movement interface in the major core and extends it beyond that. It is substantially enhanced especially in Jewish quarters favouring both Jews and Greeks by linking them to market areas.

6.2. The 1917 Plan (axial map 26)

6.2.1. Integration (maps 27,28,29)

The integration core has 45 lines, (map 27). It

- a) increases from 4 to 6 the links with the carrier (lines 1,2,5,23,28,44).
- b) creates a strong link with "Ano-Polis" (line 13).
- c) strengthens the links with parts of the traditional markets, the harbour and the developing industries westwards (lines 17,31,44,45);
- d) does not integrate the three newly-designed major clusters (Aristotelous St., St. Sophias-Acheropoetus, Rotonda-Galerian Arch-Hippodrome). Only the upper parts of Aristotelous and Rotonda clusters become integrated, while the rest of them belong to the city's most segregated lines;
- e) integrates the old Turkish administration centre converted to Ministry of Northern Greece, the old and the proposed Town Halls and other administrative buildings, and some of the old Greek churches.
- f) does not integrate major socio-cultural buildings and most of the Greek religious centres, that nevertheless, their proximity to the core is

substantially increased.

There are four major clusters of the most segregated areas:

1) Rotonda is linked through segregated lines with the Galerian Arch, St. Panteleimon and Panagia Dexia, forming thus, a segregated cluster.

2) Hippodrome and the Octagon are stretching south-wards the Galerian Arch down to the coast and include the roman palace, old Greek churches and public baths. At the bottom right-hand corner the White Tower seems to remain highly segregated.

3) Scattered lines pass through the main clusters of Aristotelous St. and the left-hand side of the proposed central market (Vlalis). Part of the old wholesale market and the earlier city's tertiary sector, remain highly segregated. A park proposed at both sides of Vardari Sq. remains highly segregated, too.

4) In "Ano-Polis", the broadening and straightening of the streets along both sides of the frontiers hardly integrated it to the overall spatial structure.

Summarising the findings in "planning units" (map 28),

a) the most accessible lines of the units are linked directly or loosely with the main accessibility core.

b) commercial streets become highly accessible.

c) the major Greek public buildings become highly accessible whereas the Turkish and Jewish ones highly segregated.

"Ano-Polis" considered as a separate subsystem, there can be noticed

a) three clusters integrating either the extensions of the city-core, or a significant part of the frontiers.

b) the most segregated lines form major clusters largely identical to the pre-1917 city's highly segregated areas (map 21).

Concluding, the 1917 Plan increased the city's links with the carrier and "Ano-Polis" and strengthened the city's major core focusing it at the city's central area functions (mainly administration and commerce). The cores of the quarters are identical or extend the city's core; in no case do they form segregated clusters.

The traditionally developed commercial streets and their extensions become highly accessible. The same applies largely to the pre-1917 markets, but not to the newly-designed ones (Vlalis-Vatikiotis-Pazarakia) and the tertiary sector in the pre-1917 plan.

Aristotelous cluster does not become highly accessible either locally or globally.

St. Sophia's-Acheropeoetous cluster is only locally highly accessible.

Rotonda-Hippodrome cluster is highly segregated.

The core was not organised mono-centrally and by no means fully integrated any of the proposed land-uses.

The Greek monuments' treatment varies from their revealing to city's points of reference (globally highly accessible) to their simple integration, in all cases easily accessible from the city's core. The public buildings and open spaces of the other ethnicities-and especially the Turkish ones-become highly segregated.

In "Ano-Polis" accessibility remains largely unaffected.

Accessibility has been increased from the city's core to the residential areas (especially the middle-and-upper class ones).

6.2.2. Control (C) -Intelligibility (I)

(maps 30,31,32,33,34)

Map 30 shows the 83 lines responsible for the 10% higher control values of the overall system. The core

a) makes full use of the city's pre-existing entrances increasing them to twelve;

b) links directly the market and harbour areas with the rest of the city and the outside world;

c) high values are achieved mainly in the market and harbour areas, the main commercial streets and the administration centre (map 31);

d) is concerned with the improvement of links in the interior of the system so that to become better locally constituted and improve its global intelligibility (lines perpendicular or diagonal to the coast); again, the four major parallels upwards Egnatia St. gain the highest intelligibility values;

e) is much more dispersed than the I.C. transcending even purely residential areas.

f) In contrast to the pre-1917 city, control values develop so that to encourage strangers to move around in areas of central functions and inhabitants to be easily accessed to the city's core: high global intelligibility flows smoothly in almost all the city's parts smoothly reduced from areas of central functions to residential ones. Again middle class areas gain higher values.

g) In Vlais-Vatikiotis-Pazarakia markets high CV lines are found along the major streets, but they do not penetrate them except in Vlais-Vatikiotis Sts where space becomes highly intelligible. This also applies to the old city's tertiary sector (low intelligibility, map 32).

h) In the south-eastern part of the city high intelligibility had been

avoided, while local constitution was substantially improved.

i) Intelligibility was also improved toward "Ano-Polis" (map 33). In this area the rationalisation of the lay-out contributed to the dispersal of lines with high CVs identified to some of the most segregated ones. Therefore, the plan improved the intelligibility of space at its borders as well as some internal routes where there are articulated some of the old public open spaces:

j) Aristotelous St. is of low control and intelligibility.

k) The cluster of St. Sophia-Acheropoetus is only locally constituted. Both of the monuments are in very high CV areas (high intelligibility) since streets perpendicular to their linking axis are lines of high CVs.

l) Rotonda-Hippodrome cluster is neither locally nor globally highly constituted (low intelligibility). Only Rotonda building is highly intelligible.

m) Most of old Turkish public buildings are weakly linked with the city's control core and thus poorly intelligible (map 31). In contrast, some of the old highly segregated Greek churches become much closer to high CV lines: the old Greek public buildings became much more intelligible than in the pre-1917 plans (one to three steps away from the highly intelligible streets).

The area around the old Turkish and now Greek government centre remains of high intelligibility.

At the twenty-eight subsystems processed (map 34) there can be noticed that constitution and intelligibility has been increased considerably in

a) the residential areas, especially the high income ones

b) the old commercial streets and market places

c) most of the old Greek public buildings (mainly churches) and the pre-

existing open public spaces

The same values have been reduced in

- a) the newly-designed market areas
- b) the three major "monumental wholenesses"
- c) most of the old Turkish and Jewish public buildings and their surrounding open spaces.

Concluding, most of the highest control values are invested on the links with the carrier, the main old commercial streets and market places, the harbour and the administration centre. The system became more intelligible from the outside, helping strangers move easily through the city's central-area functions and inhabitants to be accessed to the city's core.

The control core is concerned with the smooth distribution of movement to and within the system itself; thus, global intelligibility is encouraged to expand in purely residential areas. Ranking according to income, upper-class areas are of higher intelligibility than the middle-and-low income ones.

High intelligibility is achieved along the commercial streets, but not in the newly-designed markets of Vlais-Vatikiotis-Pazarakia as well as the area of the old tertiary sector ("Malta").

The plan improves intelligibility values along the borders with "Ano-Polis" as well as at certain parts of the area itself.

High intelligibility is achieved in none of the three major wholenesses (Aristotelous St., St.Sophia-Acheropeotous,Rotonda-Hippodrome. St. Sophia-Acheropeotous cluster becomes only locally highly constituted).

The old Greek public buildings and open spaces are found on lines of

strong control and intelligibility values or, one to two steps away from them: they became much more intelligible than in the pre-1917 plans. This also applies to a limited extent to the Greek public buildings of "Ano-Polis".

The old Turkish and Jewish public buildings gain low control and intelligibility values.

The above attributes are noticed in the scale of the "planning-unit" as well.

In general, the control and intelligibility structure of the 1917 plan appears to relate strongly to the main commercial and administration activities and relatively weakly to the core of the tertiary sector, the purely residential areas and the public thoroughfares of the other than Greek ethnicities.

6.2.3. Choice (CH) -Movement Interface (MI)

(maps 35,36,37,38,39)

Map 35 shows the 83 lines responsible for the 10% higher choice values of the system:

a) The links of the horizontal lines with the vertical and diagonal ones are rather weak: the system develops more toward favouring the links with the carrier than linking its own parts.

b) The rest of the high choice values have been invested in market areas, the newly-emerging tertiary sector, some of the old Greek social centres and "Ano-Polis".

c) There is a major overlap between the integration and choice cores (lines 30,3,41,8,9,11,17,13,63,4,65,11,59,2,54,69,15,10,74,1,60,52): the

movement interface between strangers and inhabitants is best favoured along all streets parallel and upwards Egnatia St., a commercial street perpendicular to the coast (line 15), one of the four major diagonals, the area between the old wholesale markets and the harbour as well as some areas of the newly-designed markets (map 36).

d) High inhabitant-movement lines are noticed in:

- parts of the city directly connected with the overlapping integration and choice cores: the movement flows unimpeded and smoothly reduced from the core to the purely residential areas;

- the old market areas and the most important in the old plan commercial streets; the same applies only and partly to Vatikiotis new market; Pazarakia and Vialis markets are not easily accessed by the inhabitants themselves;

e) The eastern and southeastern residential areas (upper class) are more densely linked with the central-area functions than the north-western areas (low and middle class); the old and still operating tertiary sector is of rather low density of inhabitant movement.

f) There is no high-density inhabitant movement along the three monumental wholenesses, but there are high values around some of the major public buildings, old Greek monuments and public spaces; almost all the remained Turkish public buildings are found on low IM and MI values.

g) "Ano-Polis" considered separately, major continuities of high-density routes have been achieved along its borders with Lower City as well as the city's frontiers: most of the high-choice values are invested on how the area to become more accessible from the outside than facilitate the movement of inhabitants in its heart (maps 37 and 38).

h) In the twenty-eight subsystems processed, again the high-density

inhabitant-movement lines are mostly identical to the major core, or extent it up to the heart of the planning units (map 38); this happens even in "Ano-Polis" (map 39).

i) Even in this scale there are no dense inhabitant-movement lines along all the three major monumental clusters; instead, nodes of radially-traced lines become the focus of major inhabitant movement, regardless of the uses these areas gain.

Concluding, the system develops more toward favouring the links with the carrier than linking its parts among themselves.

The movement interface is best achieved at the almost identical integration and choice cores where commercial and administration activities take place. An unimpeded flow of inhabitant movement is distributed from the above cores to the purely residential areas. The upper-class areas eastward and southeastwards are favoured most.

In Lower City the intersecting points of the radially traced streets and public buildings allocated there acquire exceptionally high IM and MI values.

High inhabitant movement and movement interface are noticed at:

- a) a small part of the newly traced market areas
- b) most of the old traditional markets
- c) some of the Greek social centres

Low IM and MI values are found at:

- a) the old tertiary sector ("Malta")
- b) the three "monumental wholenesses"

c) most of the old Turkish and Jewish public buildings.

"Ano-Polis" acquires higher values along its borders, while inhabitant movement is not equally favoured in its heart.

6.3. The mid 1970s Plan (Axial map 40)

6.3.1. Integration (maps 41,42)

The integration core consists of 36 lines (5% of the most integrated lines, map 41).

a) The links with the carrier have been increased from six to nine (lines 1,10,14,15,6,8,7) and with "Ano-Polis" from two to seven (lines 29,12,5,27,2,35,8).

b) Three out of the four major diagonals become integrated forming a sort of symmetrical rhomboid "supergrid".

The streets in the core integrate mainly commercial and tertiary sector activities mixed with recreation, health services and public buildings.

Egnatia St. running again along the whole width of the city and linking it at both sides with the carrier, integrates a variety of central-area functions; moreover, its extensions integrate the railway station, manufacturing and industry, the University Campus, military and health services as well as the International Fair.

Tsimiskis St. (lines 7 and 8) links the carrier at both of its sides and mainly integrates central-area functions (especially commercial activities).

Therefore, the four longest lines not only provide access from the outside, but most importantly, appear to be helping visitors to pass through the entire city while being in its integration core.

Makedonikis Amynis St. is actually running along the city's outer edge

linking integrated lines and forming with them a sort of "supergrid" integrating a mixture of activities (line 6). This street as well as Heptapyrgiou St. (line 8) seem to be providing extensive areas of high integrating value at the smallest possible distance from the outside. Therefore, visitors do not have to go into the city in order to have easy access to its various parts.

With respect to the four major diagonals, they link the main streets of the core and integrate commercial and office activities, housing, central-area functions and old public centres (line 33). C.B.D. expands so that to fill the "supergrid" of the major rhombus. The area westwards Aristotelous St. and southwards Egnatia St., occupied by a large part of the C.B.D. core, cloth-manufactures, wholesale and retail markets, offices of enterprises and economic institutions is highly segregated.

26th October St. (where there are allocated the city's Court-House, a centre of Health and community-care services, a telecommunications centre and the city's major coach stations) seems to be very important to the communication of the contemporary city within-the-walls with the carrier, enhanced by the fact that transpatial links are encouraged to be realised through the western extension of Tsimiskis St.

Some of the most segregated lines pass through or along Aristotelous and St. Sophia-Acheropoeitous wholenesses.

Highly segregated are also the wholesale markets of Ladadika, Modiano, the central food market (Vlalis, Vatikiotis), the harbour area and the monumental wholeness of Rotonda-Hippodrome.

The links with "Ano-Polis" penetrate the border with Lower City at its whole length (lines 29,12,5,2,35,27,8), mainly integrating residential areas, old Greek churches, commercial, recreation and special uses. The most segregated lines of "Ano-Polis" form a highly segregated and continuous

cluster. If considered as a separate system, three out of seven integrating lines overlap the city's major core and this clearly indicates that the whole area has become better integrated to the overall urban structure (map 42). Furthermore, its integration core extends the city's core linking Lower City with the northern frontiers. These routes integrate -beyond housing - commerce, recreation and light manufacture. Highly segregated remain the major old public buildings, major public open spaces and recreation centres.

Concluding, unlike the unplanned city and to a less extent the 1917 plan, the mid 1970s core does not form a closed, compact core in the centre of the city, but it has significantly increased the links with the carrier. Moreover, the city becomes much more accessible from the outside and from the core to its parts. It also becomes part of a much broader urban system, its parts becoming directly and highly accessible to the outside visitors.

Egnatia and Tsimiskis Sts are the most accessible both externally and internally streets traversing the whole city's width and integrating mainly tertiary sector and public service activities.

The major diagonals become highly accessible providing the core with symmetry with regards to the whole spatial system mainly integrating commercial and tertiary sector activities and some old social centres.

The most integrated lines include all three zones of the city's C.B.D.. High values appear at the city's western borders integrating streets that encourage the city's transpatial links. Besides, highly accessible areas appear to be those hosting commercial and cultural activities related to some old cultural centres, especially at the upper part of the core.

Housing, although better integrated than in the previous plans, is

seriously threatened by the expansion of C.B.D. eastward and northward (extended application of zoning system).

Again, high-income residential areas gain higher accessibility than low income ones. Segregated remain the major wholenesses of Aristotelous St.,Sophia-Acheropeoetous and Rotonda-Hippodrome as well as the 1917 planned market areas (Vlalis, Vatikiotis, Pazarakia), the harbour, the wholesale, food and clothe-markets.

"Ano-Polis, despite of the multiplication of the links with Lower City, remains highly segregated; when considered as a separate sub-system, it integrates some of the routes linking it with Lower City and providing the area with commercial, high manufacture and some other local services. It leaves to its most segregated areas the major old public buildings, public open spaces and recreation centres.

6.3.2. Control (C) - Intelligibility (I)

(maps 43,44,45,46)

Map 43 shows the 71 lines responsible for the 10% higher control values of the overall system.

The control core

a) distributes more symmetrically than ever the control values all over the city,

b) realises a geometric symmetry through the major diagonals of the 1917 plan that now enter the C.C. and some of the most important streets perpendicular to the coast;

c) makes full use of the city's entrances, the links with the carrier increased to fifteen.

d) involves the wholesale areas, the harbour, the newly-traced commercial streets; C.B.D.'s expansion eastward and northeastward is favoured by the high CVs developed in these areas significantly improved compared with the same area in the 1917 plan.

e) The integration and control cores are not identical except of the links with the outside world: there is a balance between the control values invested on the global and local levels (map 44).

f) The central part of the city upwards Egnatia St. is the most dense in lines of high control and intelligibility values (lines 3,38,9,52,2,6,21,1,31,10,47), except of the ancient Agora that remains with low values.

g) The major commercial streets of high CVs perpendicular to the coast do not afford high IVs; the same applies to the rest of the long lines parallel to the coast and southwards Tsimiskis St.

h) Three out of the four diagonals have high both control and intelligibility values.

i) The high control and integration values are identical mainly on lines linking the city with the carrier and the three major diagonals helping the internal distribution of visitors (high intelligibility).

j) The old wholesale markets become of higher CVS. In contrast, the area of the old tertiary sector and "Pazarakia" market remain on low CVs. The 1917-designed markets of Vlais-Vatikiotis become of higher local constitution.

k) The middle class residential areas are provided with remarkably better constitution and intelligibility than the low-class ones.

l) The cluster of Aristotelous St. is of low CVs.

m) St. Sophia-Acheropoetous cluster is of high control values: Acheropoetous and St.Sophia's churches have exceptionally high values.

n) Rotonda-Hippodrome cluster acquires high CVs. St. Sophia, Rotonda and Phanarioton sqs form a major triangle of high local constitution transcended by streets of high C and I values (lines 10, 37,3) or only high CVs (lines 35,60): they become a cluster of an exceptionally high local constitution. This local attribute is enhanced by the five parallel streets of high global CVs running parallel to the coast and penetrating the whole area up to the city's borders and beyond them. In contrast, Hippodromiou square remains poorly locally constituted.

o) Some of the other old monuments -although highly constituted-have their backs on highly segregated and low control value lines: there is a sudden disruption of the CVs developed around them.

p) Most of the old public buildings (included the Greek ones) and open spaces around them are of low CVs.

r)"Ano-Polis" major links with Lower City are on high C and I value lines (11,48,59,27,8) all along the eastern borders; the western ones have only high CVs. In the area itself the most rationalised streets become high CV lines (maps 45,46). Some of them remain highly segregated: the still isolated clusters are of high local constitution. Such places are around the major old Greek social centres and major public open spaces. The streets along the frontiers and internal to the system become of high CVs, but not all along their length; the whole area remains thus poorly constituted and intelligible. The same applies to the major routes linking Lower City with its upper frontiers: no continuity of high constitution, and hence, intelligibility.

Concluding, the mid-1970s plan has its high CV lines symmetrically distributed achieving a balance of high intelligibility between the spaces directly linked with the carrier and those internal to the system: the city

becomes more intelligible than ever from the outside and at its parts.

The C.B.D., the old market areas, the harbour, the major commercial streets, the administration centre and the main streets upwards Egnatia St., three out of the four diagonals linking major monuments and administration activities, become highly locally constituted and globally intelligible areas, while the old tertiary sector remains poorly constituted.

The major commercial streets perpendicular to the coast, and the old wholesale markets acquire only exceptionally high or high local constitution. Ladadika market remains poorly constituted.

St. Sophia-Acheropoetous and Rotonda-Hippodrome clusters acquire exceptionally high or high local constitution. Aristotelous cluster is of low local constitution. All three of them have low intelligibility values.

Some of the old Greek public buildings and socio-cultural centres become highly constituted and globally intelligible, but most of them are provided with very low values. The same applies to the old Turkish and Jewish public buildings and their surrounding open spaces.

The middle-class residential areas are much better constituted and intelligible than the low-class ones.

In "Ano-Polis" highly constituted places are scattered in the segregated clusters involving major old public buildings and open spaces. Disruption of continuity of high local constitution takes place along the borders and the major routes from Lower City to the frontiers. The area remains poorly constituted and intelligible.

6.3.3. Choice (CH) - Movement Interface (MI)

(maps 47,48,49,50)

Map 47 shows the 71 lines responsible for the 10% highest choice value of the total system.

a) The inhabitant movement with respect to the carrier is maintained high through the major ten entrances with high choice-value.

b) The system as a whole has become geometrically more symmetrical than previously through the high choice-values vertical and diagonal lines. Besides, high inhabitant movement values can be found along the city's borders perpendicular to the coast (lines 4,40):

c) High choice-value lines penetrate again the border and the heart of "Ano-Polis" that its links with Lower City have been substantially improved.

d) Most of the high values are carried by streets where commerce and administration activities develop: C.B.D.'s expansion north-eastward is favoured most.

e) The integration and choice cores superimposed, they are largely identical at the major lines of the "supergrid" (lines 4,26,17,38,30,68,71,3,9,15,51,53,6): movement interface is mainly realised along streets linking the city with the carrier, the administration and commercial area, the eastern borders and the links with "Ano-Polis"; it is slightly lower in C.B.D. and all the monumental wholenesses (map 48).

f) Therefore, strangers visit the city mostly for commerce, administration and tertiary sector services.

g) High choice and movement interface values are found along
g1) the three of the four major diagonals (the fourth one remains for local movement)